

THE INFLUENCE OF COMPENSATION, WORK MOTIVATION AND DISCIPLINE ON TEACHER'S WORK PRODUCTIVITY

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Abstract:

The objectives of this study were to find out the influence of compensation, work motivation, and discipline on work productivity of state elementary school teachers of Palembang. Data in this study were collected through distributing the questionnaires to respondents. The results of the questionnaire were analyzed by using multiple regression analysis through t-test, F-test, and the coefficient of determination. Population in this study was the Principals of all State elementary Schools of Palembang, amounting to 247 Schools. The number of samples from the population in this study was based on calculations using the Slovin formula. So, the samples in this study were 71 (seventy one) principals from all state elementary schools in Palembang. The results of the study showed that (1) there was a significant influence partially of compensation on teacher work productivity; (2) there was a significant influence partially of work motivation on teacher work productivity; (3) there was a significant influence partially of discipline on teacher work productivity; and (4) there was a significant influence simultaneously of compensation, work motivation and discipline on teacher work productivity.

Keywords: compensation, work motivation, discipline, work productivity

1. Introduction

The teacher's work productivity can be seen from the teacher's tasks in the teacher's main tasks and functions. According to Yuliandri and Kristiawan (2017) the teachers'

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performance may also improve the quality of education and quality of teaching. While Renata, et. al. (2018) state that headmaster should upgrade the supervision of teachers and achievement motivation where they would actualize the effective teachers. The type of teacher's main tasks and functions as stated in (Government Regulation No 74/2008) concerning the Teacher, Section 52, includes: a) planning the teaching and learning activities; b) implementing the teaching and learning activities; c) assessing the teaching and learning outcomes; d) guiding and training the students; and e) carrying out additional tasks.

To achieve maximum productivity there are some factors that affect work productivity of the teacher, one of which is compensation. Compensation is intended as a reward for the sacrifice of time, energy, and thoughts that have been given by the teacher in educating their students. The teacher receives a lot of compensation from the government. Compensation received by teachers, especially teachers with status as civil servants (PNS) in the form of basic salary, child and wife allowances, health insurance, pension benefits, certification allowances, teaching allowances, guarding allowances, excess teaching allowances, and foundation allowances (if teachers teach private school). All of these allowances have been budgeted in the APBD and APBN. The amount of compensation received requires the teacher to further increase his productivity in school.

The second factor that influences teacher work productivity is work motivation. According to Hamdani et al. (2018) teachers' work motivation is one of the factors in the process of improving the teachers' performance, and work motivation have a positive and significant influence on the teachers' performance (Andriani, et. al, 2018). Work motivation is a condition that encourages, stimulates or moves someone to do something or various activities to achieve a goal. It is important for a teacher to foster the spirit to continue to give all the best for their students. With the work motivation, the teacher will give the best continuously for a generation of nation which has a high quality.

In addition to compensation and motivation, other factors that influence teacher productivity are discipline. Discipline is the attitude of willingness of someone to express and obey the norms of regulations that apply around him. In carrying out his duties, a teacher must be disciplined. Sutrisno (2015) states that employee productivity in an organization is strongly influenced by employee discipline. So, a teacher must come to school on time and carry out his duties, it is expected that work productivity will increase.

SD Negeri 58 Palembang is one of the primary schools in Ilir Timur II sub-district of Palembang. Based on the results of the author's interview on February 4, 2018 with the Principal of SD Negeri 58 Palembang, it was found that the work productivity of teachers in this school was quite high. But according to the Principal, there were still few teachers whose productivity needs to be improved. Among them, there were teachers who come late often, absent to work without any excuse or prior notice. When coming to school, the teacher also did not immediately go to class, and was busy of doing something in the office. There were also few teachers who always arrive on time,

but go home earlier with any excuse. When the teacher often comes late or does not enter the class, it will certainly affect the teaching and learning activities of students in the classroom which will certainly harm the students. It shows that the teacher's work productivity needs to be improved.

In terms of work motivation, there were few teachers who come to school with the sole purpose of carrying out their main tasks, namely to teach in class. There was no motivation to carry out additional tasks given to him on the grounds that he only wants to be an "ordinary teacher" and not pursue a promotion. There were also teachers who were given additional assignments (such as being a committee in school activities) but did not want to carry out the task on the grounds there were no additional fees. There were still few teachers who were less diligent in completing work for example in completing the annual program so that there was a delay in the execution of work. This was not in accordance with the time set in a budget year. In the implementation of learning there were still few teachers who do not use learning methods in a variety of ways. Sometimes the media used cannot stimulate students' interest in learning such as attractive teaching aids so that students were less interested in learning.

In addition, still according to the principal, there were also few teachers who always arrive on time and always go to class and go home on time, but the teacher's concern was still lacking in the attitude and behavior of their students outside the classroom. So, the teacher merely teaches in class, even though the main tasks and functions of the teacher clearly are not just teaching in class. The teachers had often been called and received guidance from the principal, but there has been no significant change in the teacher's attitude. The principal did not know exactly what caused the decline in the productivity of his teacher. Because enforcement of the discipline has been pursued, they have also received compensation in the form of certification allowances which should also increase teacher motivation in teaching, so that the teacher's work motivation at elementary school is still low.

Several previous studies have been conducted in analyzing variables relevant to current research. Research conducted by Murti (2013) and Wibowo, et. al (2016) found that compensation had a significant effect on productivity. Komalia (2013), Sumakul, et. al. (2014), Pratiwi (2015), Suparman (2016) found that there were positive and significant influences of work motivation on teacher work productivity. Prihatin (2014) found that there was a significant influence on work discipline on teacher work productivity.

Description of the background and some previous research becomes the motivation of the author to conduct research to analyze the influence of the three variables, namely compensation, work motivation and discipline on teacher productivity. This research was conducted at all state elementary schools in Palembang. Problem formulation in this research were 1) whether there was significant influence of compensation on teacher's work productivity? 2) whether there was significant influence of work motivation on teacher's work productivity? 3) whether there was significant influence of discipline on teacher's work productivity?

According to Sutrisno (2015), compensation is intended as a reward from company for the employees to sacrifice the time, energy, and mind that they have given to the company. Motivation can be defined as a process that explains the intensity, direction and perseverance of a person in trying to achieve his goals. Motivation questions how to encourage subordinate work passion, so they want to work hard by giving all the abilities and skills to realize company goals (Sutrisno, 2015). Human needs can be classified into five hierarchies of needs, as follows; a) Physiological needs; b) The need for safety; c) Social relations needs (affiliation); d) Need for recognition (esteem); and e) The need for self-actualization. While, discipline is an attitude of willingness and willingness of a person to obey the prevailing rules and regulations (Sutrisno, 2015).

2. Material and Methods

This research was a correlation research, conducted by researchers to determine the level of relationship between two or more variables, without making changes, additions or manipulation of data that already exists (Arikunto, 2010). Compensation, work motivation and discipline as independent variables will be tested for their influence on teacher work productivity as the dependent variable.

In this study, the population was the Principal of all State Elementary Schools in the city of Palembang, amounting to 247 Schools. To determine the sample size of the population in this study was based on calculations by using the Slovin formula as follows (Umar, 2005)

$$n = \frac{N}{1+Ne^2}$$

Where,

n = number of samples to be taken

N = total population

e = tolerated sampling error 10%

Data obtained on March 3, 2018; the number of principals from the State Elementary School of Palembang total of 247 respondents. With a sampling error that can be tolerated at 10%, the sample size obtained was 71 respondents. Determination of the sample size for each District is calculated proportionally.

2.1 Test Instruments

The instrument used in this study was a set of questionnaire that contains a list of attached statements. In conducting the questionnaire, respondents were asked to choose one answer that suited their situation. The alternative of answers used an interval scale with "likert scale" (Sekaran, 2003), divided into five levels.

Validity testing, the validity testing used in this research was Pearson Product Moment correlation analysis, to calculate the correlation between each statement with

total score with the help of Statistical Product and Service Solution (SPSS) software version 21 on 30 sample test outside the sample. Presentation of validity at significant level used (α) = 5%, that is if r_{count} is higher than r_{table} then the variable is valid, and vice versa if r_{count} lower than r_{table} then the variable is invalid.

Reliability testing, to measure the reliability of the questionnaire in this study used Cronbach's Alpha technique with the help of Statistical Product and Service Solution (SPSS) software version 21. According to Ghozali (2013), a variable is said to be reliable if the results of $\alpha > 0.70$ and if the result of $\alpha \leq 0.70$ means unreliable.

2.2 Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics, the data that had been given by the respondents in the questionnaire that had been distributed, was processed and used to provide an overview or explanation of the respondent's response to each item of questionnaire given.

Inferential statistics, multiple regression analysis was used in analyzing the data. Multiple regression analysis done in this research was test of coefficient of determination (R^2), partial test (t-test) and simultan test (F-test). While classical assumption test conducted in this research were normality test, multicollinearity test and heteroscedasticity test.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Description of Respondents Response

Respondents' responses were arranged in the form of frequency distributions based on respondents' answers to each statement on the questionnaire indicator of compensation, work motivation, discipline, and work productivity.

3.2 Inferential Statistics Analysis

a. Normality test

It aimed to test whether the regression model, dependent variable and independent variables both had a normal distribution or not (Santoso, 2010).

Figure 1: Results of Normality Test with Histogram

Figure 1, a histogram graph, showed that the data spread around the line and followed the direction of the histogram chart forming a normal curve and most bars under the curve showed normal distribution patterns, then the regression model met the assumption of normality.

Figure 2: Results of Normality Test with Normal Probability Plot

Figure 2. showed the normal probability plot, where the data spread around the diagonal line and followed the direction of the diagonal line or the histogram graph showed the normal distribution, then the regression model met the assumption of normality.

b. Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test in this study aimed to see whether there was a particular pattern on the scatterplot chart between SRESID and ZPRED, where the Y-axis was predicted Y and the x-axis was the studentized residual (Y-predicted Y) that had been studentized (Santoso, 2010).

Figure 3: Results of Heteroscedasticity Test

Figure 3. showed that there was a distribution of data around the zero point on the Y axis, and did not appear to be a particular pattern or trend line in the distribution of the data. This means there was no heteroscedasticity and data can be used for further research.

c. Multicollinearity Test

To find out whether there was a symptom of multicollinearity in the regression model of this research was conducted through collinearity statistical test by looking at the value of Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value. Based on the analysis results, it was found that the VIF values were lower than 10 ($VIF < 10$), so it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity on the data test.

3.3 Determination Coefficient Test R^2

Table 1: Result of Determination Coefficient Test

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.591 ^a	.349	.320	5.026
a. Predictors: (Constant), Discipline, Work Motivation, Compensation				
b. Dependent Variable: Work Productivity				

Table 1. showed the value of R Square was 0.349. It showed that 34.9% of the variable teacher work productivity could be explained by the compensation, work motivation and discipline variables. While the rest ($100\% - 34.9\% = 65.1\%$) was explained by other causes outside the research variables such as competence, working conditions and others.

3.4 Partial Test (t_{test})

The t-test was done by comparing the sig. value and coefficients in Table 2 with a value of t-Table. If the statistics of t-count $<$ t-table statistics, then H_0 is accepted, and if the statistics of t-count $>$ t-table statistics, then H_0 is rejected and or if the probability is higher than 0.05, then H_0 is accepted, and if the probability of significance is lower than 0.05, then H_0 is rejected [8]. T-table 1.99547 was obtained from Table t with $df = n - k$ ($df = 71 - 3$, $df = 68$) and alpha 0.05.

Table 2: Partial Test Results (t_{test})

Coefficients ^a			
Model		T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	.146	.884
	Compensation	3.630	.001
	Work Motivation	2.865	.006
	Discipline	2.525	.014
a. Dependent Variable: Work Productivity			

3.5 The Influence of Compensation on Work Productivity

The results of the t-test for compensation variable (X_1) on work productivity (Y) showed a sig value of 0.001 meaning that the significance value was lower than the probability value of 0.05 ($0.001 < 0.05$) and t-count showed a value of 3.630, meaning that t-count was higher than t-table ($3,630 > 1,99547$). It can be concluded that H_{01} was rejected and H_{a1} was accepted, meaning that there was a significant influence of compensation on teacher's work productivity and it can be said that the compensation variable individually or partially had a significant influence on teacher work productivity. The value of compensation variable coefficient was positive indicates that the increase of compensation will be followed by an increase in teacher work productivity and vice versa the decrease of compensation, will be followed by a significant decrease of work productivity.

3.6 The Influence of Work Motivation on Work Productivity

The results of the t-test for work motivation variable (X_2) on work productivity (Y) showed a sig. value of 0.006 meaning that the significance value was lower than the probability value 0.05 ($0.006 < 0.05$) and t-count showed a value of 2.865, meaning that t-count was higher than t-table ($2,865 > 1,99547$). It can be concluded that H_{01} was rejected and H_{a1} was accepted, meaning that there was a significant influence of work motivation on teacher's work productivity and it can be said that individually or partially, work motivation variable had a significant influence on teacher work productivity. The coefficient value of the work motivation variable was positive indicates that the increase of work motivation will be followed by an increase in teacher's work productivity and vice versa the decrease of work motivation will be followed by a significant decrease in work productivity.

3.7 The Influence of Discipline on Work Productivity

The results of the t-test for discipline variable (X_3) on work productivity (Y) showed a sig. value of 0.014 meaning that the significance value was lower than the probability value 0.05 ($0.014 < 0.05$) and t-count showed a value of 2,525, meaning that t-count was higher than t-table ($2,525 > 1,99547$). It can be concluded that H_{01} was rejected and H_{a1} was accepted, meaning that there was a significant influence of discipline on teacher's work productivity and it can be said that individually or partially, discipline variable had a significant influence on teacher's work productivity. The coefficient value of the discipline variable was positive, indicates that the increase of discipline will be followed by an increase in teacher's work productivity and vice versa the decrease of discipline will be followed by a significant decrease in work productivity.

3.8 Simultaneous Test (F_{test})

This test was conducted to find out whether all independent variables of compensation, work motivation, and discipline had the same effect on teacher's work productivity as dependent variable. If the statistics of F-count $<$ F-table statistics, then H_0 is accepted, and if the statistics of F-count $>$ F-table statistics, then H_0 is rejected and or if the

probability is higher than 0.05, then H_0 is accepted, and if the probability of significance is lower than 0.05, then H_0 is rejected [8].

Table 3: Results of Simultaneous Significance Test (F_{test})

ANOVA ^a		
Model		F
1	Regression	11.969
	Residual	
	Total	
a. Dependent Variable: Work Productivity		
b. Predictors: (Constant), Discipline, Work Motivation, Compensation		

From Table 3, the results of simultaneous testing of compensation variables, work motivation and discipline were known to be calculated as 11.969 with a significance level of 0.000. F-table 3.13 was obtained by looking at table F with $df = k-1$ ($df = 3-1$) and $df = n-k$ ($df = 71-3$) at a significance level of 0.05. Because probability (0,000) was lower than 0.05 and F-count was higher than F-table ($11,969 > 3,13$), then H_{04} was rejected and H_{a4} was accepted; in other words, there was a significant influence of compensation, work motivation and discipline simultaneously on teacher's work productivity.

The partial test results (t-test) of compensation variable on work productivity found that H_{01} was rejected and H_{a1} was accepted, meaning that there was a significant influence of compensation on teacher's work productivity and it can be said that compensation variable individually or partially had a significant effect on teacher's work productivity. It also showed that, if compensation increases, will be followed by an increase in teacher's work productivity and vice versa if compensation decreases, will be followed by a significant decrease in work productivity.

The partial test results (t-test) of work motivation variable on work productivity found that H_{02} was rejected and H_{a2} was accepted, meaning that there was a significant influence of work motivation on teacher's work productivity and it can be said that work motivation variable individually or partially had a significant effect on teacher's work productivity. It also showed that, if work motivation increases, will be followed by an increase in teacher's work productivity and vice versa if work motivation decreases, will be followed by a significant decrease in work productivity.

The partial test results (t-test) of discipline variable on work productivity found that H_{01} was rejected and H_{a1} was accepted, meaning that there was a significant influence of compensation on teacher's work productivity and it can be said that discipline variable individually or partially had a significant effect on teacher's work productivity. It also showed that, if discipline increases, will be followed by an increase in teacher's work productivity and vice versa if discipline decreases, will be followed by a significant decrease in work productivity.

4. Conclusion

There was a significant influence of compensation partially on teacher work productivity; There was a significant influence of work motivation partially on teacher work productivity; There was a significant influence of discipline partially on teacher work productivity; and there was a significant influence of compensation, work motivation and discipline simultaneously on teacher work productivity.

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